

Alumni.in

REVIEW OF SDGS IN
EMERGING COUNTRIES
E-ISSN: 2965-7393

VOLUME 5 (2023)

PERSPECTIVES ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: THE INTERSECTION OF PUBLISHING AND ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN ADVANCING SDGS

SUBMITTED ON OCTOBER 10, 2022.
APPROVED ON JANUARY 1, 2023.
VOLUME 5 (2023).

HOW TO CITE (APA):

SILVA, A. DE O., & JANES, D. DOS S. (2023). PERSPECTIVES ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: THE INTERSECTION OF PUBLISHING AND ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN ADVANCING SDGS. REVIEW OF SDGS IN EMERGING COUNTRIES, 5(00), E0029. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.37497/2965-7393.SDGS-COUNTRIES.V5.N00.29](https://doi.org/10.37497/2965-7393.SDGS-COUNTRIES.V5.N00.29)

ABSTRACT

This viewpoint paper explores the integral roles of the publishing industry and Scopus, an eminent academic research tool, in supporting and advancing the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The analysis begins by highlighting the crucial impact of publishing in disseminating information that heightens SDG awareness. It then delves into the SDG Publishers Compact, an initiative led by the United Nations and the International Publishers Association, examining its development, objectives, and the specific commitments it entails. This Compact represents a pivotal move towards embedding sustainable practices within the publishing sphere. Further, the paper evaluates Scopus' significant stride in incorporating SDGs into its research database, with a special focus on the addition of SDG17 in 2023. This inclusion underscores the necessity of collaborative research efforts in addressing complex global challenges. The challenges and opportunities that arise from implementing the Compact's objectives are discussed, providing insights into the complexities involved. The paper concludes by projecting future directions in sustainable publishing and the anticipated role of data science in SDG-focused research, emphasizing the synergistic impact of publishing and academic tools in driving forward the agenda for sustainable development.

Keywords:

Sustainable Development Goals, Publishing Industry, SDG Publishers Compact, Scopus, Sustainability in Research

ALTIERES DE OLIVEIRA SILVA

EDITORA ALUMNI IN (São Paulo).

Ph.D. candidate in Business Law and Citizenship at UNICURITIBA, I specialize in Open Access Scientific Journals. I hold a certification from Cambridge University in Scientific Publication. With expertise in the field of Business Law and a strong focus on promoting accessibility to scientific knowledge.

DIEGO DOS SANTOS JANES

EDITORA ALUMNI IN (São Paulo).

I hold a Bachelor's degree in Business Administration from UNINOVE, and I am an expert in Open Access Scientific Publications, specializing in Scientific Communication and Editorial Management. Additionally, I have a specialization in Corporate Governance, which complements my knowledge and skills in the realm of business and organizational management. With a focus on promoting accessibility to scientific knowledge and effective editorial practices, my academic background equips me with a comprehensive understanding of both business administration and scholarly publication processes.

In an era marked by unprecedented global challenges, including climate change, inequality, and a pressing need for sustainable development, the role of the publishing industry and academic research tools like Scopus in advancing the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has never been more significant. This paper provides a perspective on the transformative potential of these entities in promoting a sustainable future, examining the impact of publishing on SDG awareness, the evolution of the SDG Publishers Compact, Scopus' role in integrating SDGs, and the broader implications of these initiatives. Through this lens, we explore how information dissemination, policy-making, and academic research are interlinked in the pursuit of global sustainability goals.

The Rising Importance of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development, as conceptualized by the United Nations, is a multidimensional goal that seeks to achieve a balance between economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental sustainability. The Sustainable Development Goals, a set of 17 interlinked goals adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, are a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity by 2030. These goals recognize that ending poverty and other deprivations must go hand-in-hand with strategies that improve health and education, reduce inequality, and spur economic growth – all while tackling climate change and working to preserve oceans and forests (United Nations, 2020).

The Transformative Role of Publishing

The publishing industry has a unique and powerful role in this context. As a purveyor of information and knowledge, the industry is uniquely positioned to influence public awareness, education, and policy-making related to sustainable development. Publishers, by disseminating research and literature that align with the SDGs, can play a pivotal role in shaping public understanding and discourse on these critical issues. They can provide a platform for voices and ideas that drive action towards these global goals, thereby contributing significantly to the global movement towards a more sustainable and equitable world.

Introduction of the SDG Publishers Compact

Recognizing this influential role, the United Nations, in collaboration with the International Publishers Association, introduced the SDG Publishers Compact in 2020. This initiative represents a commitment from the publishing industry to support and promote the SDGs. The Compact outlines specific targets for publishers to align their operations with the goals and objectives of sustainable development. These targets range from promoting SDG-aligned content and advocating for sustainability to engaging in collaborative efforts and dedicating resources towards SDG projects. The Compact is not just a symbolic gesture but a practical framework for integrating sustainability into the heart of publishing practices.

Scopus' Integration of SDGs

In parallel, academic research tools like Scopus are playing a vital role in aligning scientific research with the SDGs. Scopus, a comprehensive abstract and citation database, has integrated SDGs into its system, marking a significant step in aligning academic research with the global sustainability agenda. The inclusion of SDG17 in 2023, focusing on partnerships for achieving the goals, along with updates to other SDGs, demonstrates a growing recognition of the interconnected nature of research and sustainable development. By labeling research publications with SDGs, Scopus not only enhances the visibility of SDG-related research but also facilitates a more informed and targeted approach to research funding and prioritization. Times Higher Education (THE) are using the Elsevier SDG data mapping as part of their [Impact Rankings](#).

Empowerment sustainability perspectives for Bahraini women as...

[View PDF](#) [Full text options](#) [Export](#)

Abstract	empower entrepreneurs, to enhance the empowerment of women entrepreneurship in the Kingdom of Bahrain. © 2023 China Ordnance Society
Author keywords	Author keywords
Sustainable Development Goals 2023	Bahraini women; SDG 11; SDG 4; SDG 5; SDG 8; SDG 9; SDGs; Women empowerment; Women entrepreneurship
SciVal Topics	
Metrics	Sustainable Development Goals 2023 New

Sustainable Development Goals mapped to this document

Gender equality

Goal 5

Decent work and economic growth

Goal 8

Reduced inequalities

Goal 10

Partnership for the goals

Goal 17

ELSEVIER
Scopus

Times Higher Education
Impact Rankings
2023 TOP 80

EXPLORE IMPACT RANKINGS FOR INDIVIDUAL SDGS

OVERALL RANKING	1 NO POVERTY	2 ZERO HUNGER	3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	4 QUALITY EDUCATION	5 GENDER EQUALITY	6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION	7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH
9 INDUSTRY INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION	13 CLIMATE ACTION	14 LIFE BELOW WATER	15 LIFE ON LAND	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS

The Synergy Between Publishing and Academic Research Tools

The synergy between the publishing industry and academic research tools in promoting SDGs is a testament to the power of information and knowledge in driving change. Publishers, by adopting the Compact's commitments, can influence the direction and focus of research, public discourse, and policy-making related to sustainable development. Simultaneously, research tools like Scopus, by integrating SDGs, can guide researchers towards areas of critical need and relevance in the sustainability context.

Advancing Awareness and Action

The impact of these initiatives goes beyond mere awareness-raising; it catalyzes action. By aligning content with SDGs, publishers not only inform their audiences but also inspire them to take action towards these goals. They become partners in a global effort to address some of the most pressing challenges of our time. This alignment also opens up opportunities for new collaborations and partnerships, bringing together diverse stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and civil society in a united effort towards sustainable development.

Challenges and Opportunities in Implementation

Implementing the SDG Publishers Compact's targets and integrating SDGs into research tools like Scopus presents its own set of challenges. It requires a commitment of resources, a shift in organizational culture, and the development of new strategies and partnerships.

However, these challenges are outweighed by the opportunities they present. For publishers, this means not only a chance to contribute to global sustainability efforts but also to innovate and lead in an industry that is increasingly recognizing the importance of social and environmental responsibility. For academic research tools, this means playing a pivotal role in shaping the direction of scientific inquiry and its impact on society.

The SDG Publishers Compact, initiated by the United Nations and the International Publishers Association in 2020, outlines commitments to align the publishing industry with SDGs (United Nations, 2020). It includes specific targets such as promoting SDG-aligned content and advocating for sustainability, reflecting the industry's dedication to this global agenda. The SDG Publishers Compact, a collaborative initiative between the United Nations and the International Publishers Association, outlines a series of specific commitments that publishing entities are encouraged to adopt to support the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These commitments are designed to align the publishing industry with the broader global agenda of sustainability and social responsibility. **The key targets of the SDG Publishers Compact are as follows:**

- **Committing to the SDGs:** Publishers are expected to publicize their sustainability policies and targets, including adherence to this Compact, and to incorporate the SDGs and their targets into their operations as appropriate.
- **Promoting SDG-Aligned Content:** There is an active push to acquire and promote content that advocates for themes represented by the SDGs, such as equality, sustainability, justice, and environmental stewardship.

- **Annual Reporting on SDG Progress:** Publishers are encouraged to report annually on their progress towards achieving the SDGs, sharing data and contributing to benchmarking activities. This involves sharing best practices and identifying gaps that need attention.
- **Nominating an SDG Coordinator:** Each signatory is expected to appoint an individual within their organization who will promote SDG progress, acting as a point of contact and coordinating the SDG themes throughout their operations.
- **Raising Awareness Among Staff:** Publishers are encouraged to raise awareness and promote the SDGs among their staff, increasing awareness of SDG-related policies and goals, and encouraging projects that will help achieve the SDGs by 2030.
- **Engaging Suppliers on SDGs:** This involves raising awareness and promoting the SDGs among suppliers, advocating for the SDGs, and collaborating on areas that require innovative actions and solutions.
- **Advocacy to Customers and Stakeholders:** Publishers commit to becoming advocates to customers and stakeholders by promoting and actively communicating about the SDG agenda through their marketing, websites, promotions, and projects.
- **Collaborative Efforts:** The Compact encourages collaborating across cities, countries, and continents with other signatories and organizations to develop, localize, and scale projects that will advance progress on the SDGs, either individually or through their Publishing Association.
- **Dedicating Resources for SDG Projects:** Signatories are expected to dedicate a budget and other resources towards accelerating progress for SDG-dedicated projects and promoting SDG principles.
- **Taking Action on Specific SDG Goals:** Each publisher, individually or through their national publishing association, should take action on at least one SDG goal and share their progress annually.

These targets represent a comprehensive approach to embedding sustainability and social responsibility within the publishing industry. By adhering to these principles, publishers not only contribute to the global agenda of sustainable development but also reinforce their commitment to creating a positive social and environmental impact.

The Importance of Collaboration and Partnerships

The inclusion of SDG17, "Partnerships for the Goals," in Scopus' 2023 update underscores the importance of collaboration in achieving the SDGs. Sustainable development is a complex and multifaceted challenge that requires the collective effort of all sectors of society. By fostering partnerships, both within the publishing industry and between publishers, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders, we can leverage a wide range of expertise, resources, and perspectives in pursuit of the SDGs.

Looking Ahead: Future Trends and Predictions

As we look to the future, it is clear that the role of publishing and academic research tools in advancing sustainable development will only grow in importance. We can expect to see an increase in content focused on sustainability issues, more collaboration between publishers and other stakeholders, and greater use of data science and technology in aligning research with the SDGs. These trends will be driven by a growing recognition of the critical role that information and knowledge play in achieving sustainable development, as well as by the increasing demand from readers, researchers, and funders for content and tools that contribute to this global agenda.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of the SDGs into the publishing industry and academic research tools represents a significant step forward in the global effort to achieve sustainable development. By raising awareness, driving research, and fostering collaboration, these initiatives are helping to create a more informed, engaged, and proactive global community. The challenges in implementing these initiatives are real, but so are the opportunities they present for innovation, leadership, and impact. As we move towards the 2030 deadline for the SDGs, the role of publishing and research in advancing these goals will be crucial. By working together, we can harness the power of information and knowledge to create a more sustainable, equitable, and prosperous world for all.

Alumni IN Publishing's Bold Move: Signing the United Nations SDG Publishers Compact

Alumni IN Publishing reaffirms its role as a catalyst for sustainable and responsible research, dialogue, and knowledge dissemination. The publisher's diverse portfolio, including the "Review of SDGs in Emerging Countries," will now play an even more crucial role in shaping a sustainable future, guided by the principles and objectives of the SDG Publishers Compact.

This commitment positions Alumni IN Publishing at the forefront of scholarly and practical discussions on sustainable development, especially in regions that are vital to achieving global sustainability goals.

References

McCullough, R. (2023). 2023 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) now available on Scopus. Retrieved from <https://blog.scopus.com/posts/2023-sustainable-development-goals-sdgs-now-available-on-scopus>

United Nations. (2020). SDG Publishers Compact. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sdg-publishers-compact/>